

CONCEPTUAL-FUNCTIONAL SIGNIFICANCE OF DRAMATIC COMPONENTS IN CULTURAL EVENT SCRIPTS

Mamatqosimova Nodira Eshquvatovna
Senior Lecturer, Department of “Culture and Art Management”
Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture

Annotation. This article explores the conceptual-functional significance of dramatic components within the scripts of cultural events and offers an in-depth analysis of their compositional structure. Each dramatic component is examined in terms of its conceptual meaning.

Keywords: culture, art, dramaturgy, dramatic component, cultural event, script, compositional structure.

Introduction. The preparation of scripts for cultural events is an inherently creative process, wherein the identification and analysis of dramatic components assume a conceptual-functional character. The script must be constructed in such a way that any reconstruction, removal, addition, or modification of its parts does not, akin to how altering a rhyme or word in poetry would distort the whole, compromise the integrity of the artistic work.

Literature review and methodology. A dramatic work must possess a clearly articulated unity. In order to ascertain what type of unity is being implied in commonly accepted discourse, it is necessary to clarify this for ourselves. Centuries of global dramaturgical practice have demonstrated that, to preserve the artistic integrity of a dramatic piece, adherence to the unities of time and place in the represented action is not strictly required. However, the unity of action is of paramount importance [1, p. 182].

Action serves as the central conflict driving the development of a play, and maintaining the unity of action ensures the holistic representation of the subject matter. Violating this unity inevitably leads either to a distortion of the subject being depicted or to an inability to convey it in a comprehensive manner [2, p. 56].

Within the script, the elements of dramaturgical composition, much like the action-driven conflict in a play, constitute a unified action. At the foundation of any dramatic work lies a compositional structure that is principal and universally applicable. This structure comprises the following elements:

- the initiation of the conflict;
- the progression of the conflict;
- the resolution of the conflict.

As noted by researcher F.E.Akhmedov, “Hegel paid particular attention to this aspect. As a result, this structural framework in dramaturgy has come to be referred to as the ‘Hegelian triad’” [1, p. 184].

Nevertheless, every play must possess a composition that is structurally precise and rich in content. From the perspective of proportion, the relationship between the parts within a play’s structure is limitless in its variations and bears individual characteristics. Despite this diversity, dramaturgical composition and its elements represent a unified typology, with a shared structural basis and foundation. Just as an ending cannot exist without a beginning, and just as no work can

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4

progress without evolving from beginning to end, there can be no composition that concludes where it begins.

For this reason, it is essential to closely examine the core elements and functions of dramaturgical composition within the script of a cultural event.

The event composition is the structure that links the occurrences within a work through a unifying idea directed toward a single goal, in accordance with the laws of dramaturgy. The compositional structure of cultural events generally includes such components as: prologue (introduction), main event, development of events, complication, conflict, climax, and resolution.

However, in some cases – particularly within certain types of cultural events – elements such as complication, conflict, or resolution may be absent. This is because such events are not fully theatrical in nature, and their underlying idea and purpose are often expressed primarily through the content of songs and the movements of dance.

The theme is the selected subject of the event, which must be of comprehensive interest to the local population and serve as the unifying factor for all occurrences presented.

The idea is the central concept advanced by the event. The clarity and strength of this idea must be such that the audience remains engaged. Therefore, the revelation of the idea should be timed for the conclusion of the event. Throughout the performance, the audience should be encouraged to contemplate the social idea and its core message, thereby deepening their interest.

In practice, however, many organizers present the idea in a finalized form at the very beginning of the event. This approach reduces audience engagement and diminishes the overall value of the event.

The objective is the message the event intends to communicate to the audience. Every scriptwriter and director must ask themselves, prior to the creation of the work: “What do I intend to convey to the audience through this piece?” and, accordingly, ensure that the work itself provides a meaningful response. The goal of the event is expressed through a sequence of events that gradually unfold throughout the narrative.

The prologue is the introductory segment of the work, designed to inform the audience about the essence of the event. It directs their attention to the main developments. This segment should evoke an elevated mood, aesthetic beauty, and elegance. Documentary materials, film excerpts, and emotionally impactful tools can be widely used here. The prologue can begin not only on stage but also in the entryways or paths leading to the venue where the event is held.

The main event follows the prologue and acts as a trigger for the unfolding of subsequent events. Here, the theme and objective of the event may be subtly emphasized.

Development of events refers to a series of actions that contribute to the narrative and thematic complexity of the event. This phase typically includes complications, conflict, struggle, confrontation, and the overcoming of obstacles.

The complication is the point at which the audience’s thoughts and emotions become focused on a specific enigma – typically marked by the protagonists encountering unexpected developments. The complication should serve to intensify the conflict and propel the main events forward.

The conflict is an occurrence that stands in opposition to the event’s purpose or meaning, or to the behavior of the characters within the piece. The stronger the conflict, the greater the audience’s interest in the event becomes [3, pp. 27-28].

While the script of a cultural event may exert a powerful emotional influence on the audience and actively engage them as participants in the festivity, it does not necessarily require the audience

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4

to align themselves emotionally with one or another character in conflict. For this reason, the presence of conflict is not an obligatory feature of every cultural event script.

For example, celebratory events such as Navruz, Mehrjon, First Step, and various folk festivals may omit conflict altogether, especially when theatrical elements are minimal or entirely absent.

Climax is the most captivating and intense peak of the event. It naturally leads toward the resolution. The episode in which the climax is expressed must be powerful enough to directly stir the thoughts and emotions of the audience.

Finale is the conclusion of the piece – the final and most crucial part. At this stage, all narrative threads are resolved. The finale is typically delivered in an elevated, festive mood and concludes with the cheerful, exuberant participation of all performers. If the finale lacks emotional resonance, it may weaken the audience's overall impression and diminish the artistic value of the work. In some cases, the finale may be expressed through the collective appearance of all performers on stage or the communal performance of a song.

Discussion and results. Just like in literature, the compositional structure of cultural events may vary in order. For instance, the complication and conflict may follow the prologue, or their positions may be reversed. Such variations are not considered errors, as they are grounded in the thematic and conceptual framework of the event.

The degree to which a script adheres to general dramaturgical principles – namely, whether each episode is dramaturgically complete and whether the overall emotional impact and imagery grow consistently from beginning to end – defines its artistic merit.

Nevertheless, a performance script differs in style from a theatrical play or an artistic film script. In the publicistic aspect of cultural events, significant social phenomena are typically not depicted through personal conflicts of specific characters, but rather through the epic principle of emphasizing the broader significance of a social conflict.

The scriptwriter of a cultural event may incorporate excerpts from dramatic works or compose original dramatic fragments that represent the confrontations of clearly defined characters. Additionally, the script may integrate other art forms – such as music, song, choreography, sports and plastic performances, film and video segments, poetry, and so on.

Naturally, the more artistic devices are employed in a script, the more complex its execution becomes. However, constructing a thematically and artistically cohesive work is thereby made more feasible. For this reason, the dramaturgy and compositional resolution of a script hold great importance.

Although a cultural event script is capable of producing a multifaceted emotional effect on the audience, it does not always engage them in personally experiencing the emotional states of individual characters involved in a conflict. Therefore, the presence of a conflict is not a necessary requirement in the structure of a cultural event script. In some thematic scenarios, conflict may be entirely absent.

If a given episode in the script includes a powerful social conflict that reflects the times, the entire script will likely be built around its depiction. However, in cultural events, achieving strong emotional impact does not require reliance on a single stylistic approach.

A distinct feature of cultural event scripting lies in its responsiveness to the vision of the scriptwriter and director – this includes the use of vivid imagery and visual expressiveness. In cultural festivities or folk celebrations, the function of exposition may be fulfilled by the participants'

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4

theatrical procession. Likewise, poetic interludes, excerpts from plays, film fragments, and songs may serve the role of complication and thematic development.

In conclusion, it must be emphasized that compositional structure is a critical element of a cultural event – it is the key artistic factor that determines the event's expressiveness and visual appeal.

References:

1. Ahmedov F.E. Ommaviy bayramlar rejissurasi asoslari. – Toshkent: Aloqachi, 2008. – 424 b.
2. Charlz W.D. Xarakter in Art Dram & stage show. – United Kingdom, England, Artcross, 2002. – 188 p.
3. Mamatqosimov J.A. Ommaviy bayramlar rejissurasida sahna madaniyati. – Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2009. – 208 b.